

XRD-based crystallinity degrees and formation temperature of graphite in some regional-metamorphic rocks from the Central and Eastern Rhodopes, Bulgaria: a test of the new graphitization degree $GD_{(0-30)}$ scale

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Abstract. Graphitization degrees and temperatures of the regional metamorphism in the Central and Eastern Rhodopes have been determined by the values of the structural parameter d_{002} (Å) of graphite in graphite-bearing marbles and shists, from Vacha and Madan-Erma Reka areas (Madan lithotectonic unit), Ardino–Nedelino area (Startsevo lithotectonic unit), and Chernichevo–Boturche area (Byala Reka lithotectonic unit). Equations of different authors, formulated between 1951 and 2021, were used. They are integrated in one system, allowing a conversion of the results and deriving new quantitative correlations between the temperature of metamorphism, the structural parameter d_{002} (Å) and the degree of crystallinity order of semi-graphite and graphite. The comparison of the data allows the creation of a new scheme, $GD_{(0-30)}$, based on the values of the parameter d_{002} (Å) of the natural carbon matter. The validity range of this geothermometer is large, from 84 °C to 804 °C (from zeolite to granulite facies of the regional metamorphism). The temperature peak of metamorphism in the studied areas is 660 °C (i.e., the upper limit of the amphibolite facies), and the lowest temperature is 468 °C, which is characteristic for the lower part of the greenschist facies P-T field. The temperature range and graphitization degrees of the regressive metamorphism in the Central and Eastern Rhodopes are: 660 °C ($GD_{(0-30)} = 24$, well-crystallized graphite); 588 °C ($GD_{(0-30)} = 21$, graphite); 564 °C ($GD_{(0-30)} = 20$, graphite); 516 °C ($GD_{(0-30)} = 18$, graphite); 492 °C ($GD_{(0-30)} = 17$, graphite); and 468 °C ($GD_{(0-30)} = 16$, graphite). The calculated temperatures of metamorphism in the Central and Eastern Rhodopes, by equations of all authors, correspond to the conditions of metamorphism established by other methods without using of the structural parameter d_{002} (Å) of the graphite. The $GD_{(0-30)}$ system for determination of graphitization degree of the natural carbon is simple, informative and functional. It is more convenient than earlier schemes showing correlation: metamorphic temperature – d_{002} (Å) – graphitization degree. In addition to the influence of the temperature, the values of the degrees of graphitization also include the effect of all secondary factors on the graphitization processes.

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INTRODUCTION

Determining the ideal structure of hexagonal (2H) graphite (Hassel and Mark, 1924; Bernal, 1924) allows monitoring of the deviations from it. A large number of XRD analyses have been used to

determine the degree of structural ordering (graphitization degree) of natural carbon substances. Different schemes for classification of varieties of carbon matter, according to their graphitization degree, have been created in the period of 1951–2021. They are all based on the parameter

d_{002} (Å). It corresponds to the distance between the adjacent layers in the crystal structure of natural carbon matter. Thus, the graphitization degree is defined as a function of d_{002} (Å) values of carbon matter (Franklin, 1951; Kwiecinska, 1980; Seehra and Pavlovic, 1993; Ivashita *et al.*, 2004). Other authors made a connection between the structural parameter d_{002} (Å), the formation temperature and the graphitization degree of the carbon substance. This dependence allows a determination of facies of graphite-bearing metamorphic rocks (French, 1964; Grew, 1974; Wada *et al.*, 1994; Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021). There are different methods for determining and ways of expressing the degrees of structural order of the graphitized natural carbon substance after different authors (u , DOG, D.G %, DG and GD). The degrees of graphitization (u) (after Franklin, 1951; Kwiecinska, 1980) and (DOG) (after Seehra and Pavlovic, 1993) are expressed as part of one. Ivashita *et al.* (2004) formulated an indicator (D.G%), which is almost identical to DOG (Seehra and Pavlovic, 1993), but gives the respective share as percentage. The degrees of graphitization DG (Wada *et al.*, 1994) and GD (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2019, 2020) are expressed in whole as one-digit, two-digit and three-digit numbers. Some equations calculate correlations between degrees of graphitization, formulated by different authors in the system: d_{002} (Å) – graphitization degree – temperature of metamorphism – facies of metamorphism. The comparison of the data allows the creation of a new scheme – GD_(0–30) (Vlahov, 2021). The change of one degree in the range 0–30 corresponds to the change of temperature by 24 °C and of d_{002} (Å) – with 0.001 Å. The real range of this geothermometer is very large, from 84 °C to 804 °C. This scheme is convenient, and with corresponding equations, can be correlated with values of graphitization degrees (u , DOG, D.G%, DG and GD), according to different authors for the period of 1951–2021. The parameter d_{002} (Å) is the most reliable criterion for the degree of structural order of the natural carbon substances and it is a function mainly of the temperature of the metamorphic processes. The values of d_{002} (Å) and graphitization degrees are also influenced by many secondary factors: effect of general pressure and tectonic stress, structure of primary carbon matter, orientation of carbon formations, origin of primary carbon substances, fluids, mineral and chemical composition of primary carbon matter and hosting sedimentary rocks, duration of processes and complex effect of all factors (Vlahov, 2021, and references therein).

PROBLEM STATUS

Sharma *et al.* (1998), Howe *et al.* (2003) and Parthasarathy *et al.* (2003) claimed that graphite preparations for powder XRD analysis are always textured to a great extent, thus leading to intensity lowering or to disappearance of peaks other than 001 series. Such peaks should be used with caution in calculating the structural order of the natural carbon. For this reason, many authors work with well-textured samples only, and they use a parameter d_{002} (Å) as an indicator for studying the processes of graphitization and the respective metamorphic evolution of rocks.

Direct use of d_{002} (Å) values of natural carbon substances

French (1964) separated four stages of structural state of the carbon substance, by the appearance, shape and position of peak 002 in the diffractograms: 1) amorphous carbon substance (peak 002 is missing); 2) stage of coal and asphalt (the presence of a very broad and diffuse peak at about 3.5 Å); 3) structurally disordered graphite (diffuse peak at about 3.43 Å; and 4) well-crystallized graphite (a sharp peak at 3.36 Å).

Grew (1974) studied the structural state of carbon in rocks with varying degrees of metamorphism from different parts of the world. He found out that, with the increase of the metamorphic impact, the width of peak 002 and the value of d_{002} (Å) decrease. He pointed out that the first stage in the arrangement of the layers of graphite structure under conditions of regional metamorphism corresponds to a temperature of 300–500 °C and a pressure of 3 kbar (or more) and to 1000 °C and 1 kbar in contact metamorphism conditions. The complete arrangement of the graphite structure is performed at 660–690 °C and 4.5–5 kbar.

Yanchuk and Laz'ko (1980) determined a degree of structural ordering of graphite, using values of d_{002} (Å). Graphite with high structural order ($d_{002} = 3.350–3.355$ Å) is characteristic in rocks of high-temperature facies.

Based on studies of natural graphite and semi-graphite, it is established (Kwiecinska, 1980; Kwiecinska *et al.*, 2010) that cryptocrystalline carbon aggregates have $d_{002} = 3.400$ Å, and those with $d_{002} = 3.371$ Å were characterized as cryptocrystalline and microcrystalline semi-graphites. The carbon substance with $d_{002} = 3.364–3.354$ Å was defined as graphite.

Calculation of graphitization degrees on the basis of d_{002} (Å) values of natural carbon matter

The magnitude of the structural disorder (ρ) is related to the d_{002} (Å) value. The change of ρ from 0 to 1 corresponds to the change of d_{002} from 3.354 Å (fully ordered graphite) to 3.440 Å (completely disordered graphite). Franklin (1951) formulated the following relationship between d_{002} (Å) and ρ :

$$(1) d_{002} (\text{Å}) = 3.440 - 0.086 (1 - \rho^2).$$

The degree of structural order (u) is determined by the following equation (2):

$$(2) u = 1 - \rho.$$

Kwiecinska (1980) used the degrees of graphitization u of Franklin (1951) and classified natural carbon into four groups: anthracite ($u = 0.06-0.27$); meta-anthracite ($u = 0.27-0.45$); semi-graphite ($u = 0.45-0.57$) and graphite ($u = 0.57-1.00$).

Seehra and Pavlovic (1993) formulated the equation (3) for calculating of degree of graphitization (DOG). They used the values d_{002} (Å) for completely disordered graphite (3.440 Å) and for fully ordered graphite (3.354 Å) (according to Franklin, 1951) and real d_{002} (Å) value of the natural carbon matter.

$$(3) \text{DOG} = (3.440 - d_{002}, \text{Å}) / (3.440 - 3.354).$$

Ivashita *et al.* (2004) modified the equation (3) of Seehra and Pavlovic (1993) and determined the degree of graphitization (D.G %) as:

$$(4) \text{D.G \%} = [(3.440 - d_{002}, \text{Å}) / (3.440 - 3.354)] \times 100.$$

The relationship between the degree of graphitization (DG) and temperature is determined (Wada *et al.*, 1994) by equations (5) and (5a):

$$(5) T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} = 3.2 \times \text{DG} + 280;$$

$$(5a) \text{DG} = (T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} - 280) / 3.2.$$

The correlation between the temperature of metamorphism ($T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$), d_{002} (Å), and the graphitization degree (GD) was calculated directly (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020) using the following equations (6, 7, 8, and 8a).

Grew (1974) pointed out that the first stage in the arrangement of the layers of the graphite structure under the conditions of regional metamorphism corresponds to a temperature of 300–500 °C. The

experiment of Shengelia *et al.* (1979) showed that the increase of temperature was faster than the decrease of d_{002} (Å) of the carbon substance due to the insufficient time of the experiment. This leads to a nonequilibrium system in the middle parts of the temperature range. The temperature of 300 °C corresponds to $d_{002} = 3.371$ Å at the beginning of the experiment, at 708 °C, $d_{002} = 3.354$ Å, and at $T = 800$ °C, $d_{002} = 3.350$ Å (the end of the experiment). These are the three points that form a straight line and where the results are not distorted due to the short duration of the experiment. The analysis of the new straight line shows that the decrease of d_{002} (Å) by 0.001 Å corresponds to the increase of temperature by 24 °C. These facts are mathematically related in equation (6). The calculations and comparative analysis in tabular and graphical form of the data of Wada *et al.* (1994) and Vlahov (2015, 2017, 2019) show that 8 degrees of graphitization correspond to a temperature range of 24 °C (0.001 Å) and each degree corresponds to a temperature change of 3 °C. This is the basis for formulating equations (7), (8) and (8a).

$$(6) T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} = 300 + (3.371 - d_{002}, \text{Å}) \times 24000;$$

$$(7) \text{GD} = (3.371 - d_{002}, \text{Å}) \times 8000;$$

$$(8) T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} = 3 \times \text{GD} + 300;$$

$$(8a) \text{GD} = (T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} - 300) / 3.$$

The combination of equations (6), (7), (8), and (8a), with the other cited above equations and facts, allows to derive new correlations (Vlahov, 2020). The degree of graphitization $u = 0.45$ marks the boundary between meta-anthracite and semi-graphite (Kwiecinska, 1980). A decrease of temperature by 24 °C corresponds to increase of d_{002} value by 0.001 Å, according to equation (6). The application of this regularity shows that $d_{002} = 3.380$ Å and a metamorphism temperature of 84 °C correspond to the degree of structural ordering of the carbon substance in the meta-anthracite–semi-graphite series, with a limit value of $u = 0.45$, but under the condition that all secondary factors support the process of graphitization (Vlahov, 2020, 2021). These are the data based on which the equation (9) was formulated. Calculation of the degree of graphitization DOG with equation (3) shows that at $u = 0.45$, DOG = 0.69767. The difference between two consecutive DOG degrees is 0.01163. The data allow the empirical derivation of equations (10) and (11).

$$(9) T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} = (3.380 - d_{002}, \text{Å}) \times 24000 + 84;$$

$$(10) T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} = [(DOG - 0.69767)/0.01163] \times 24 + 84;$$

$$(11) T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} = [(D.G\% - 69.767)/1.163] \times 24 + 84.$$

The analysis of all possible solutions of equations (1) to (11) in the interval $d_{002} = 3.440\text{--}3.350 \text{ \AA}$ led to the formulation of six new regularities (Vlahov, 2021).

Seehra and Pavlovic (1993) formulated the equation (3) for calculating the degree of graphitization (DOG). They used the values d_{002} (\AA) for completely disordered graphite (3.440 \AA) and for fully ordered graphite (3.354 \AA) (*sensu* Franklin, 1951) and related them in the expression $3.440 - 3.354 = 0.086$. This result is the constant used in equation (1) (Franklin, 1951). Therefore, the equation (3) is easily transformed into equation (12). Equations (14) and (15) are analogous to (12) and (13), but the results are expressed as percentages (Ivashita *et al.*, 2004). The equations (13) and (15), where the degree of disorder of the structure of natural carbon matter (ρ) is present with an accuracy of 0.01 (Franklin, 1951), show insignificant deviations in the results for DOG and D.G %, which are of no practical significance. Solving all equations (1) to (15) with decreasing d_{002} (\AA) values of semi-graphite and graphite from 3.380 \AA to 3.350 \AA in the temperature range 84–804 $^\circ\text{C}$ and tabulating them show the direct relationship between d_{002} values (\AA) and the degree of graphitization as a function of temperature. Summarizing the data, significant optimization of the number of graphitization degrees in the semi-graphite–graphite order, from 0 to 30, is possible by equations (16) and (17). The degrees of graphitization in this scheme are represented by whole numbers and correspond to the change of the temperature of metamorphism by 24 $^\circ\text{C}$ in the temperature interval 84–804 $^\circ\text{C}$ and to the parameter d_{002} (\AA), by 0.001 \AA , from 3.380 \AA to 3.350 \AA (Vlahov, 2021).

$$(12) DOG = (3.440 - d_{002}, \text{\AA})/0.086;$$

$$(13) DOG = 1 - \rho^2;$$

$$(14) D.G\% = [(3.440 - d_{002}, \text{\AA})/0.086] \times 100;$$

$$(15) D.G\% = (1 - \rho^2) \times 100;$$

$$(16) GD_{(0-30)} = (T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} - 84)/24;$$

$$(17) T \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} = GD_{(0-30)} \times 24 + 84.$$

The graphitization degrees depend on the same factors as the values of d_{002} (\AA). The numbers of graphitization degrees (u , DOG, D.G%, DG, GD,

and $GD_{(0-30)}$) are different, but they change proportionally to the change of temperature and degree of metamorphism (Vlahov, 2021). All formulated equations are combined in one system for correlation, transformation and unification of data for d_{002} (\AA), temperature of metamorphism, and numerical values of graphitization degrees proposed by different authors. The proposed new scale $GD_{(0-30)}$ is a result of combination and integration of all cited facts and calculations.

XRD RESULTS OF GRAPHITE FROM CENTRAL AND EASTERN RHODOPE

Graphite-bearing rocks from the Central and Eastern Rhodopes are distributed in four main areas: Vacha area, Madan-Erma Reka area, Ardino–Nedelino area and Chernichevo–Boturche area (Fig. 1). Fourteen graphite samples were studied using powder XRD measurements. All they were ground and purified with HCl and HF to remove carbonate and silicate minerals. Textured samples for determining the interplanar distance d_{002} (\AA), were prepared from the graphite residue, following the requirements for sample preparation and conditions for conducting the analysis are specified in the works of Vlahov (2017, 2019).

Graphite-bearing rocks and XRD results of graphite from Vacha area

Values of the structural parameter d_{002} (\AA), the graphitization degrees and the temperature of metamorphism, were determined for 5 samples of graphite-bearing marbles from the Byalata Skala (White Rock) quarry, located ~13 km south of the town of Krichim and ~2 km north of the Vacha Dam. According to Sarov *et al.* (2009), the graphite-bearing marbles and associated gneisses from the Vacha area belong to the Madan lithotectonic unit. The marbles from the studied part of the Byalata Skala outcrop have a maximum thickness of 95.9 m and are located above garnet-biotite gneisses. They are interbedded with schist, gneiss and pegmatite bodies, with a thickness of 0.7–1.2 m. The marbles are grey, grey-white and white. Medium-grained varieties predominate, but in different parts of the quarry there are also small- and large-grained varieties of marbles. Structures of graphite-bearing marbles are schistose, banded, massive, rarely veined. They are impregnated by graphite flakes and aggregates (Vlahov, 2005). The mineral composition of the graphite-bearing car-

Fig. 1. Graphite occurrences in the Central and East Rhodopes: 1) Vacha area; 2) Madan-Erma Reka area; 3) Ardino–Nedelino area; 4) Chernichevo–Boturche area (Vlahov, 2017, 2019).

bonate rocks in the Byalata Skala quarry is as follows: calcite (85.0%); dolomite (10.0%); feldspar (1.0%); pyrite + iron hydroxides + titanite (0.5%); graphite (0.7–0.8%); clay minerals + phlogopite + mica + quartz + epidote + amphibole + garnet; silicates (2.5%) (Stoykov *et al.*, 1986; Trashliev, 1989; Vlahov, 2005, 2017, 2019). The results of the XRD analyses are shown in Table 1.

Graphite-bearing rocks and XRD results for graphite from Madan–Erma Reka area

The Madan–Erma reka area is located SE of Madan and north of the Erma Reka River. The graphite-bearing marbles and gneisses from this region are included in the Madan lithotectonic unit (Sarov *et al.*, 2006, 2007). The values of the structural parameter d_{002} (Å), the degrees of graphitization and the temperature of metamorphism were determined for 2 samples of graphite-bearing marbles. The latter are located to the southeast of Petrovitsa ore deposit in the Madan ore field. Graphite-bearing marbles are composed mainly of calcite (90–98%). The secondary minerals are: graphite, muscovite, pyroxene, quartz, plagioclase and pyrite. Their total amount does not exceed a

few percents. Graphite forms hexagonal crystals up to 2 mm in diameter. The massive structure of the marbles is determined by the carbonate grains with sizes of several millimeters and clear boundaries between them. The schistose and schistose-banded structures were formed by the arrangement of graphite flakes and short-prismatic crystals on the schistose planes formed under tectonic stress. The spotted structure was formed by the irregular arrangement of white, light grey to darker grey carbonate areas in the volume of the graphite-bearing marbles. Graphite individuals and aggregates are located mainly in grey and less frequently in white carbonates and can form nests. Graphite-bearing gneisses are represented by biotite, pyroxene-biotite, amphibole-biotite, amphibole-pyroxene-biotite and kyanite-biotite varieties. The most common are the biotite gneisses. They are dark grey to light brown rocks and consist of plagioclase (30%), quartz (30%), biotite (30%) and potassium feldspar (5%). The secondary minerals in them are: garnet, apatite, zircon, alantite, titanite, pyrite, magnetite, sericite, chlorite and carbonates. Visually, graphite is about 2–3% (Vlahov, 2017, 2019). The results of the powder XRD analyzes are shown in Table 2.

Table 1

XRD of graphite from Byalata Skala quarry: values of d_{002} (Å), graphitization degrees (u , DOG, DG, D.G %, GD) after different authors, magnitude of structural disorder (g), it is ρ in the text, p. 3, eq. (1), (2) structural state of carbon matter and temperature of the regional metamorphism

Sample No.	BS-1	BS-2	BS-3	BS-4	BS-5
Analytical system	HUBER Imaging Plate Camera G670	HUBER Imaging Plate Camera G670	HUBER Imaging Plate Camera G670	Powder diffractometer Siemens 500	Powder diffractometer Siemens 500
d_{002} (Å)	3.356	3.356	3.356	3.359	3.364
Graphitization degree u (Franklin, 1951) (Eq. 1, 2)	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.76	0.66
Structural state of carbon matter (French, 1964)	Well- crystallized graphite	Well- crystallized graphite	Well- crystallized graphite	Well- crystallized graphite	Graphite
Structural state of carbon matter (Grew, 1974)	Graphite with complete structural arrangement	Graphite with complete structural arrangement	Graphite with complete structural arrangement	II nd stage of graphitization	I st stage of graphitization
Structural state of carbon matter (Kwiecinska, 1980), according to values of u (after Franklin, 1951)	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite
Graphitization degree DOG (Seehra and Pavlovic, 1993) (Eq. 3)	0.97674	0.97674	0.97674	0.94186	0.88372
Graphitization degree DG (Wada <i>et al.</i> , 1994) (Eq. 5a)	119	119	119	96	59
Graphitization degree D.G % (Ivashita <i>et al.</i> , 2004) (Eq. 4)	97.674	97.674	97.674	94.186	88.372
Structural state of carbon matter (Kwiecinska, 2010) according d_{002} (Å) values	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite
Graphitization degree GD (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2019) (Eq. 7, 8a)	120	120	120	96	56
Graphitization degree DOG (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 12, 13)	0.97674 (12) 0.97750 (13)	0.97674 (12) 0.97750 (13)	0.97674 (12) 0.97750 (13)	0.94186 (12) 0.94240 (13)	0.88372 (12) 0.88440 (13)
Graphitization degree D.G % (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 14, 15)	97.674 (14) 97.750 (15)	97.674 (14) 97.750 (15)	97.674 (14) 97.750 (15)	94.186 (14) 94.240 (15)	88.372 (14) 88.440 (15)
Graphitization degree GD ₍₀₋₃₀₎ (after Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 16)	24	24	24	21	16
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Wada <i>et al.</i> , 1994) (Eq. 5)	660	660	660	588	468
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2019) (Eq. 6, 8)	660	660	660	588	468
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Vlahov, 2021): (Eq. 9, 10, 11, 17)	660	660	660	588	468

Graphite-bearing rocks and XRD results of graphite from Ardino–Nedelino area

The graphite-bearing metamorphites from the Ardino–Nedelino area are marbles, gneisses and schists and belong to the Startsevo lithotectonic unit (Sarov *et al.*, 2008). The graphite from these marbles was studied by XRD methods (Table 3). Their structure is massive to schistose. Some marbles have grey,

light-grey and white spots, which give them a spotty appearance. Graphite occurs mainly in the gray areas. Some marbles are cataclased and recrystallized. The main mineral is calcite, which makes up 90–95 % of the rock. Dolomite forms small bands and lenticular formations or its grains are located in the calcite volume. The secondary minerals in the graphite-bearing marbles from this area are: graphite, pyroxene, amphibole, quartz, muscovite, phlogo-

Table 2

XRD of graphite from Madan ore field: values of d_{002} (Å), graphitization degrees (u , DOG, DG, D.G %, GD) after different authors, magnitude of structural disorder (q), structural state of carbon matter and temperature of the regional metamorphism

Sample No.	876-1	876-2
Analytical system	Powder diffractometer Siemens 500	Powder diffractometer Siemens 500
d_{002} (Å)	3.363	3.362
Graphitization degree u (Franklin, 1951) (Eq. 1, 2)	0.68	0.70
Structural state of carbon matter (French, 1974)	Graphite	Graphite
Structural state of carbon matter after Grew (1974)	I st – II nd stage of graphitization	II nd stage of graphitization
Structural state of carbon matter (Kwiecinska, 1980) according values of u after (Franklin, 1951)	Graphite	Graphite
Graphitization degree DOG (Seehra and Pavlovic, 1993) (Eq. 3)	0.89535	0.90698
Graphitization degree DG (Wada <i>et al.</i> , 1994) (Eq. 5a)	66	74
Graphitization degree D.G % (Ivashita <i>et al.</i> , 2004): (Eq. 4)	89.535	90.698
Structural state of carbon matter (Kwiecinska, 2010), according to d_{002} (Å) values	Graphite	Graphite
Graphitization degree GD (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2019) (Eq. 7, 8a)	64	72
Graphitization degree DOG (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 12, 13)	0.89535 (12) 0.89760 (13)	0.90698 (12) 0.91000 (13)
Graphitization degree D.G% (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 14, 15)	89.535 (14) 89.7600 (15)	90.6980 (14) 91.0000 (15)
Graphitization degree $GD_{(0-30)}$ (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 16)	17	18
T °C of regional metamorphism (Wada <i>et al.</i> , 1994) (Eq. 5)	492	516
T °C of regional metamorphism (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2019) Eq. 6, 8)	492	516
T °C of regional metamorphism (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 9, 10, 11, 17)	492	516

pite, ore minerals and zircon. Graphite is represented in small quantities and is distributed irregularly mainly along boundaries of carbonate grains. Later-formed minerals are thin carbonate veins, small quartz nests, chlorite, clay-mica assemblages and iron hydroxides.

Graphite bearing rocks and XRD results of graphite from Chernichevo–Boturche area

The graphite-bearing rocks from the Chernichevo–Boturche area are marbles and schists, which are part of the Byala Reka lithotectonic unit (Sarov *et al.*, 2007a). Graphite-bearing marbles south of Chernichevo Village were studied. Their visible thickness varies from a few meters to 10 meters and more. The main rock-forming minerals are the carbonates, and the secondary ones are graphite, quartz, mica, clay minerals and single feldspar grains. The graphite flakes have sizes from parts of mm to about 1.0 mm. They are irregularly distributed in the carbonate mass. Pieces of black graphite-bearing schists with a fine schistose structure were

found in Chernata Planina (Black Mountain) area, located between the villages of Boturche and Chernichevo. Their mineral composition is represented by quartz, fine graphite particles, biotite, muscovite, sulfide mineral and iron hydroxides. Pieces of black graphite schist with apparently high content of fine-grained to massive graphite were found approximately 1.5 km west of Boturche Village. The values of the structural parameter d_{002} (Å), graphitization degrees and the temperature of metamorphism were determined in 2 samples of graphite-bearing marbles and 2 samples of graphite-bearing schists from this locality (Table 4).

DISCUSSION

Temperature is the main factor influencing the value of d_{002} (Å) and the degree of graphitization of natural carbon. Secondary factors that may enhance or reduce the effect of temperature are: effects of the general pressure and tectonic stress, the structure of primary carbon matter, the orientation of

Table 3

XRD of flake graphite in marbles from Ardino–Nedelino area: values of d_{002} (Å), graphitization degrees (u , DOG, DG, D.G%, GD) after different authors, magnitude of structural disorder (g), structural state of carbon matter and temperature of the regional metamorphism

Sample No.	890	898	899	8911
Analytical system	HUBER Imaging Plate Camera G670	DRON 1.5 M	DRON 1.5 M	DRON 1.5 M
d_{002} (Å)	3.356	3.356	3.356	3.360
Graphitization degree u (Franklin, 1951) (Eq. 1, 2)	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.74
Structural state of carbon matter (French, 1964)	Well-crystallized graphite	Well-crystallized graphite	Well-crystallized graphite	Well-crystallized graphite
Structural state of carbon matter after Grew (1974)	Graphite with complete structural arrangement	Graphite with complete structural arrangement	Graphite with complete structural arrangement	II nd stage of graphitization
Structural state of carbon matter after (Kwiecinska, 1980) according values of u (after Franklin, 1951)	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite
Graphitization degree DOG (Seehra and Pavlovic, 1993) (Eq. 3)	0.97674	0.97674	0.97674	0.93023
Graphitization degree DG (Wada <i>et al.</i> , 1994) (Eq. 5a)	119	119	119	89
Graphitization degree D.G % (Ivashita <i>et al.</i> , 2004) (Eq. 4)	97.674	97.674	97.674	93.023
Structural state of carbon matter (Kwiecinska, 2010) according d_{002} (Å) values	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite
Graphitization degree GD (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2019) (Eq. 7, 8a)	120	120	120	88
Graphitization degree DOG (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 12, 13)	0.97674 (12) 0.97750 (13)	0.97674 (12) 0.97750 (13)	0.97674 (12) 0.97750 (13)	0.93023 (12) 0.93240 (13)
Graphitization degree D.G % (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 14, 15)	97.674 (14) 97.750 (15)	97.674 (14) 97.750 (15)	97.674 (14) 97.750 (15)	93.023 (14) 93.240 (15)
Graphitization degree GD _(0–30) (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 16)	24	24	24	20
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Wada <i>et al.</i> , 1994): (Eq. 5)	660	660	660	564
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2019) (Eq. 6, 8)	660	660	660	564
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Vlahov, 2021) (Eq. 9,10, 11, 17)	660	660	660	564

carbon formations, the origin of primary carbon matter, fluids, mineral and chemical composition of primary carbon matter and host rocks, the processes' duration and the complex effect of all factors. These problems were discussed in detail in the publication of Vlahov (2021, and references therein). The combination of mechanical, thermal and other impacts can lead to the decrease of the structural order of formed carbon individuals and aggregates (Vlahov, 2017, 2019, 2021; Kirilova *et al.*, 2018).

The reversibility of the structural state of graphite allows tracing the metamorphic evolution of graphite-bearing rocks (Vlahov, 2021).

Kostov *et al.* (1986) identified four stages of mineral formation in the Central Rhodopes, where graphite mineralizations belong to the rocks of the Madan lithotectonic unit. During the first stage of progressive regional metamorphism, the serpentinization of the ultrabasic magmatic bodies begins with formation of minerals from a greenschist fa-

Table 4

XRD characteristics of graphite from Chernichevo–Boturche area: values of d_{002} (Å), graphitization degrees (u , DOG, DG, D.G%, GD) after different authors, magnitude of structural disorder (q) structural state of carbon matter and temperature of the regional metamorphism

Sample No.	9050, 9050a marble (Chernichevo)	890 schist (Chernichevo)	132 schist (Boturche)
Analytical system	HUBER Imaging Plate Camera G670	HUBER Imaging Plate Camera G670	HUBER Imaging Plate Camera G670
d_{002} (Å)	3.359	3.359	3.363
Graphitization degree u (after Franklin, 1951) (Eq. 1, 2)	0.76	0.76	0.68
Structural state of carbon matter (after French, 1964)	Well-crystallized graphite	Well-crystallized graphite	Graphite
Structural state of carbon matter after Grew (1974)	II nd stage of graphitization	II nd stage of graphitization	I st –II nd stage of graphitization
Structural state of carbon matter (after Kwiecinska, 1980) according values of u (after Franklin, 1951)	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite
Graphitization degree DOG after Seehra and Pavlovic (1993) (Eq. 3)	0.94186	0.94186	0.89535
Graphitization degree DG (after Wada <i>et al.</i> , 1994) (Eq. 5a)	96	96	66
Graphitization degree D.G % (Ivashita <i>et al.</i> , 2004) (Eq. 4)	94.186	94.186	89.535
Structural state of carbon matter (Kwiecinska, 2010), according to d_{002} (Å) values	Graphite	Graphite	Graphite
Graphitization degree GD after Vlahov, (2015, 2017, 2019) (Eq. 7, 8a)	96	96	64
Graphitization degree DOG after Vlahov (2021) (Eq. 12, 13)	0.94186 (12) 0.94240 (13)	0.94186 (12) 0.94240 (13)	0.89535 (12) 0.89760 (13)
Graphitization degree D.G % after Vlahov (2021) (Eq. 14, 15)	94.186 (14) 94.240 (15)	94.186 (14) 94.240 (15)	89.535 (14) 89.760 (15)
Graphitization degree GD _(0–30) after Vlahov (2021) (Eq. 16)	21	21	17
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Wada <i>et al.</i> , 1994) (Eq. 5)	588	588	492
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Vlahov, 2015, 2017, 2019) (Eq. 6, 8)	588	588	492
T °C of the regional metamorphism (Vlahov, 2021): (Eq. 9, 10, 11, 17)	588	588	492

cies. The progressive metamorphism ends with the maximum sinking of the complex at about 25 km, forming rocks with the decisive participation of quartz, garnet I, kyanite I, mica, amphibole, oligoclase-andesine and potassium feldspar. Other minerals that are formed under these P-T conditions are tourmaline I, graphite I, fine-flake to dusty in gneisses and fine-flake to large-flake in marbles. The peak of the progressive regional metamorphism in the studied area is at a temperature of about 600–635 °C and pressure between 11 kbar and 9 kbar. The pressure value of 8 kbar, at a T = 600 °C, is

considered to be the closest to the actual one. The pressure of 8 kbar also corresponds to the maximum stability of the paragenesis of staurolite + quartz (Pertchuk and Ryabchikov, 1976; Pertchuk, 1981). The values of 8 kbar and 9–11 kbar at a temperature of 600 °C fall in the field of the kyanite-muscovite facies (BC₃), which is most acceptable for the deep metamorphism of the rocks of the Central Rhodope group (Kostov *et al.*, 1986).

During the second (anathetic-pegmatite) stage, for the maximum of regional granitization and migmatization, the most probable values of temperature

and pressure are ~ 675 °C and $\sim 6,5$ kbar, respectively, as determined in the area of Stoykite Village in the Central Rhodopes (Kostov *et al.*, 1986). Migmatization is typical for the deep parts of the metamorphic complex in the Central Rhodopes, where temperatures exceed 600 °C, and mineral associations in metapelites mark a transition from stability kyanite field to sillimanite field (Arnaudova *et al.*, 1990). The final, pegmatite-skarn and microcline-oligoclase, stage corresponds to the uplift and consolidation of the metamorphic complex and the formation of intersecting pegmatites with sharp boundaries with the host rocks. Typical accessory minerals are columbite, struverite, beryl I, tourmaline III, graphite II, garnet II (almandine), and others. (Kostov *et al.*, 1986). The last stages of mineral formation (*i.e.*, pegmatoid and hydrothermal) are not directly related to the processes of graphite formation in the Central Rhodopes.

The data for the Eastern Rhodopes (the region of Zlatograd) can be correlated with the sections of the Madan unit: the maximum temperatures of metamorphism reach the lower levels of the sillimanite zone (620–660 °C). Other studies on the thermobaric conditions indicate temperatures of 580–550 °C and pressures of 6–9 kbar (staurolite-kyanite zone). The regressive metamorphism leads to lower temperature and low-pressure conditions (garnet zone) – 550–440 °C and 4–2 kbar (Ovtcharova, 2005). Macheva and Kolcheva (1992) used a synkinematic metamorphic association (quartz + albite + biotite + phengite + garnet) and determined a temperature range from 450 °C to 650 °C and a wide pressure variation of 4 kbar to 14 kbar for the metamorphic rocks from the Byala Reka unit. The pressure (5–8 kbar)

was calculated based on the Si-content in fengite. Additional studies determined values of $P > 5$ kbar and $T > 430$ °C. Studies of white mica from metagranites, gneisses and schists from the whole region of Byala Reka unit show that the rocks have undergone polyphase metamorphism. The first phase is associated with a rapid thickening of the crust in continental collisions and the metamorphism is high-pressure/low-temperature type (HP/LT) at a minimum pressure of 13 kbar and a temperature of about 450 °C. The metamorphism is medium-pressure/medium-temperature (MP/MT) with a pressure of 9–3 kbar and a temperature of approximately 500 °C during the second phase of rapid lifting and unloading of the crust. Low-pressure/low-temperature metamorphism (LP/LT) at a pressure of 3–2 kbar and a temperature of 400 °C takes place during the third phase of cooling of the crust (Macheva, 1998).

The present studies of the graphite mineralizations in all four areas in the Rhodopes (Fig. 1) show that graphite was formed under conditions of progressive regional metamorphism at the level of amphibolite facies. Graphite-bearing rocks have undergone later regressive changes at the greenschist facies level. Structures and mineral composition of the graphite-bearing rocks represent a reliable record of the transition from amphibolite to greenschist facies.

The greyer nuances of graphite-bearing marbles are not due to fine graphite particles dispersed in them. Their grey colour is determined by the relatively high contents of dolomite, silicates, ore and other minerals associated with graphite. These minerals are more resistant to dissolution than calcite under the influence of fluids in regressive changes.

Fig. 2. Structures of graphite-bearing marbles from the Byalata Skala quarry, Vacha area: *a*, *b*) graphite ring with two openings; *c*) formation of a late graphite vein (Vlahov, 2017, 2019).

Fig. 3. Structures of graphite-bearing marbles from the Madan ore field: *a, b*) deformed graphite flakes, which mark direction of movement in a shear zone; *c, d*) mechanically deposited graphite from fluids in tectonic faults (Vlahov, 2017, 2019).

They are distributed and concentrated mainly in the grey areas of the marbles by the fluids of regressive metamorphism (Figs. 2, 3).

The high-temperature minerals formed under the conditions of the amphibolite facies of the progressive regional metamorphism are tectonized and corroded by the fluids or replaced by the low-temper-

ature minerals during the regressive metamorphism (Fig. 4).

The thermal characteristics and scanning electron microscopy of graphite from the Rhodopes also support this finding (Vlahov, 2017, 2019). XRD methods have established the relationship between d_{002} (Å) and degree of structural order of graphite,

Fig. 4. Optical microscopy of graphite-quartz schists from Chernichevo-Boturche area: *a*) cross polarized light and *b*) plane polarized pictures of cracked and corroded garnet crystal (Grt) with small-flake to powder graphite (Gr) after Vlahov (2017, 2019).

Table 5
Lithotectonic units, areas and sampling points, graphite-bearing rocks, d_{002} (Å), $GD_{(0-30)}$ values and T °C of metamorphism

Lithotectonic unit	Area (sampling points)	Graphite-bearing rocks	Number of samples	d_{002} (Å)	$GD_{(0-30)}$	T °C of the regional metamorphism
Madan	Vacha area, Byalata Skala quarry	marble	3	3.356	24	660 °C – peak of the regional metamorphism
Madan	Vacha area, Byalata Skala quarry	marble	1	3.359	21	588 °C – retrograde metamorphism
Madan	Vacha area, Byalata Skala quarry	marble	1	3.364	16	468 °C – retrograde metamorphism
Madan	SE from Petrovitsa deposit, p. 876 (N 41°25'50.52"; E 24°57'08.64")	marble	1	3.362	18	516 °C – retrograde metamorphism
Madan	SE from Petrovitsa deposit, p. 876 (N 41°25'50.52"; E 24°57'08.64")	marble	1	3.363	17	492 °C – retrograde metamorphism
Startsevo	p. 890 (N 41°24'51.58", E 25°03'30.17"); p. 898 (N 41°29'30.44", E 25°03'32.45"); p. 899 (N 41°29'35.89", E 25°03'06.41")	marble	3	3.356	24	660 °C – peak of the regional metamorphism
Startsevo	Chernichevo–Boturche area, SW from Chernichevo Village, p. 8911 (N 41°31'40.33", E 25°13'38.99")	marble	1	3.360	20	564 °C – retrograde metamorphism
Byala Reka	Chernichevo–Boturche area, SW from Chernichevo Village, sample 9050 (N 41°20'47.22", E 25°46'7.86")	marble	1	3.359	21	588 °C – retrograde metamorphism
Byala Reka	Chernichevo–Boturche area, sample 890–1, Chernata planina (between Chernichevo and Boturche villages)	schist	1	3.359	21	588 °C – retrograde metamorphism
Byala Reka	Chernichevo–Boturche area, W from Boturche, sample 132 (N 41°22'46.26", E 25°55'7.22.30")	schist	1	3.363	17	492 °C – retrograde metamorphism

which are a function of temperature. The degrees of structural order of graphite, calculated by the equations of different authors, show regular changes in temperatures during the transition from amphibolite to greenschist facies. The $GD_{(0-30)}$ graphitization scale (Vlahov, 2021) is sufficiently informative and convenient to use (Tables 1–4). It is a result of the correlation of the data on the structural order of the

natural carbon substance of different authors for the period 1951–2021. Equations (9, 16, 17) show the relationship between temperature and graphitization degree $GD_{(0-30)}$ and the structural parameter d_{002} (Å). Their application in the studies of graphite from the Rhodopes is shown in Table 5. The informational significance and application of the $GD_{(0-30)}$ scale are illustrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Graphitization degree $GD_{(0-30)}$, calculated with eq. (16) vs. d_{002} (Å) values of carbon matter, its structural state according to graphitization degree u values after Franklin (1951) and classification of Kwiecinska (1980) with metamorphic temperature (T °C) data for graphite-bearing rocks from the Central and Eastern Rhodopes.

CONCLUSIONS

The tested new $GD_{(0-30)}$ scale for determination of the structural order of natural carbon matter and the temperature evolution of metamorphism is convenient to operate because:

- 1) The degrees of graphitization form a regular continuous numerical order from 0 to 30;
- 2) The change with one degree of graphitization corresponds to a change of temperature of metamorphism by 24 °C and by 0.001 Å of the structural parameter d_{002} (Å) of the semi-graphite and graphite, which were formed under conditions from zeolite to granulite facies of the regional metamorphism (84–804 °C). This accuracy is sufficient for the purposes of mineralogical research, facial diagnostics of metamorphic rocks, and forecasting the industrial properties of graphite. Graphite raw materials with a higher degree of structural order also have better technological properties;
- 3) The $GD_{(0-30)}$ system is based on equations which can be easily transformed for another initial temperature, without changing the calculation principle;
- 4) The $GD_{(0-30)}$ system avoids the excessive detail of earlier systems for reporting a degree of graphitization of natural carbon matter;
- 5) The reversibility of the structural state of graphite allows tracing the metamorphic evolution

of graphite-bearing rocks. Specimens from places located far enough from the tectonic fault, processed and hydrothermally altered, zones contain “relics” of graphite with structural characteristics approximately corresponding to the peak of the progressive metamorphism. The structural characteristics of graphite from the regressively changed parts of the rocks are underestimated and correspond to the conditions of the retrograde metamorphic stage;

6) All structural data must be confirmed by the mineral composition and the order of mineral formation in the rocks. The study of contradictions between the instrumental data ($GD_{(0-30)}$ system) of the carbon material and the mineral composition of the host rocks leads to the discovery of new facts about the metamorphic history of carbon-bearing rocks;

7) The calculated temperatures of metamorphism in the Central and Eastern Rhodopes by the new $GD_{(0-30)}$ system corresponds to conditions of metamorphism established by other methods without using of structural parameter d_{002} (Å) of graphite.

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